

NEW EDITION OF THE CONSTITUTION OF UZBEKISTAN AND LEGAL CULTURE OF EMPLOYEES OF STATE INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *The Constitution (as amended) defines the main guarantees of a high level of development of legal culture in the country, which apply to employees of government agencies.*

The possibility of achieving effective formation of legal culture and legal consciousness of employees of government institutions with their active participation in intellectual and educational competitions or in advanced training courses is shown.

It is noted that the high level of legal culture of employees of state institutions and the state of their legal consciousness and legal behavior indicate a high level of maturity of the country's legal system.

It is noted that the course "Theories of State and Law" allows employees of government agencies to correctly assess complex state and legal phenomena of public life.

Keywords: *in intellectual and educational competitions, legal phenomena of public life, emergence of provisions.*

Factors shaping legal culture and legal consciousness.

The qualitative state of the legal life of society, determined in conjunction with the social, spiritual, political and economic system, is characterized by the state of legal culture in the country. Legal culture is not just an attitude towards the law, but a respectful attitude towards it and therefore, as a rule, it is characteristic of a state with a developed system of civil society.

For example, even the title of the third section has been changed and now it is not just "Society and the Individual," but "Civil Society and the Individual." In addition, many articles in this section have been significantly supplemented with new progressive additions (Nos. 53-56,61, 63-65). Realizing the high responsibility to present and future generations, they constitutionally enshrine:

- recognition of the priority of building and strengthening a humane, democratic, legal, social and secular state that cares about the honor, dignity, well-being and interests of every person;
- the emergence of provisions on building an open, fair and harmonious civil society;
- confirmation of loyalty to the ideals of democracy (social justice, freedom and equality);
- the desire to ensure the sustainable development of the country, a decent life for young people through the development of a sustainable system of education, science, culture and spirituality;

- stimulating the development of diverse forms of increasing the level of legal awareness of society and citizens of the country;

- comprehensive development of the legal culture of society and the individual, based on historical, cultural, spiritual values and cultural heritage of great ancestors.

On the legal culture of employees of government agencies.

Many innovations in the new version of the Constitution largely concern employees of government agencies who have direct contact with the rest of the country's population. In the Constitution, legal concepts are not abstractions divorced from life, but express reality and concrete social relations in a condensed form.

With the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in a new edition and the program for the development of New Uzbekistan, the intensification of work on the formation of a legal culture and legal consciousness began in the country with renewed vigor [1,2].

In the new conditions, employees of government agencies must understand, first of all, the socio-philosophical step-by-step understanding of the specifics of the very concept of a new legal culture. Especially in relationships with ordinary citizens, an employee of a government agency is obliged to conduct them with respect for people, in compliance with all norms of law and ethics. And for this you need to know them, carefully instill in yourself and master all the rules and concepts of legal culture. An employee of a government agency can and should achieve effective formation of legal culture and legal consciousness by participating in various kinds of educational processes (competitions, intellectual competitions or advanced training courses).

The legal culture of an individual employee of a government agency is a combination of spiritual, legal, political, pedagogical and other types of his culture. Such a complex and responsible task requires a more detailed study and assimilation of basic scientific, social and public aspects, comprehensive norms of legal culture and legal consciousness.

A high legal culture of employees of government agencies is the basis of any democratic society and an indicator of the maturity of the country's legal system.

The concept of a person's legal culture and its analysis shows its closest connection with legal consciousness and legal behavior. Legal awareness is a form of social consciousness, including a set of legal knowledge and legal values that serve as motivational factors for individual behavior. Legal behavior is understood as socially significant behavior of individual and group subjects.

The study of legal culture involves considering it as a social phenomenon with certain distinctive principles and approaches of legal and philosophical-legal methodological orientation. Research into legal culture should address such important subject areas as problems of social determination of cultural and legal phenomena, ethno-psychological aspects of legal mentality and legal culture.

It is necessary to study life by deeply comprehending its basic legal concepts laid down in the new edition of the Constitution, many qualitative aspects of which, as well as a set of necessary knowledge, can be obtained by studying the course "Theories of State and Law." It is this discipline that allows employees of government institutions to competently qualify political and legal situations, from a scientific point of view to give a correct assessment of the complex state-legal phenomena of public life, to reveal their true essence, and to understand their social purpose. Studying the course "Theories of State and Law" will allow

- competently develop the professional qualities of employees,
- increase the level of their legal awareness and legal culture,
- largely determine the success of democratic reforms and the country's progressive movement towards the formation of a civil society.

Conclusion

- The main constitutionally enshrined guarantees of a high level of development of legal culture in the country have been identified.

- It has been established that many innovations in the new version of the Constitution concern employees of government agencies due to the specifics of their activities - they work directly in contact with the rest of the country's population.

- It is argued that the effective formation of the legal culture and legal consciousness of employees of government agencies is achieved through their active participation in intellectual and educational competitions, competitions or advanced training courses.

- It is noted that in any democratic society, a high level of legal culture of employees of government agencies is an indicator of the maturity of the country's legal system.

- It is shown that from the analysis of the concept of a person's legal culture, it follows that there is a very close connection with the concept of legal consciousness and legal behavior.

- It is noted that studying the course "Theories of State and Law" allows one to qualify certain political and legal situations from a scientific position, correctly evaluate complex state and legal phenomena of public life, reveal their true essence, and understand their social purpose.

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